
PHILOSOPHICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL BASES OF EDUCATION

Mr. Maheshkumar C. Patel (M.A., M.Ed. SET, M.Phil.)

*Principal, Meghwad Primary School,
Taluka- Kaprada, Dist. Valsad, Gujarat*

ABSTRACT

Education is a process to facilitate learning, to acquire knowledge, to apply knowledge, to develop understanding and skills. Education may take place formally or informally. Learners may learn with direct or indirect approaches through experiences. Education is a process of modification of child's behavior. General objectives of education are to impart knowledge, understanding, application of knowledge and developing skills, habits, interest etc. Main functions of education are related to development of an individual, society and the nation. There are various purpose of educational philosophy such as inspirational purpose, analytical purpose, prescriptive purpose and inquiry purpose that focus on different areas of education. Educational philosophy is a separate branch of philosophy which deals with framing the objectives of education and nature of education. It sets the goals of education according to the specific religion, society, morals and scientific approaches. Further it provides directions to achieve those objectives of the education. Educational psychology is the branch of Psychology which deals with various areas of education such as learning, behavioral psychology, theories of learning, motivation, intelligence, adolescent period, objectives of education, need of education, curriculum etc. There are three main perspectives of education where we find psychological base of education i.e. behaviorism, cognitivism, constructivism.

Meaning of Education

The word 'Education' is derived from the Latin word, 'Educare' which means 'to bring up', 'to nourish'.

Definitions

1. Aurobindo defines education as, 'Education means helping the growing soul to draw out that is in itself'.
2. According to Swami Vivekananda, 'Education is the manifestation of divine perfection already existing in man'.
3. Rabindranath Tagore states that- Education means enabling the mind to find out that ultimate truth which emancipates us from the bondage of the dust and gives us wealth, nor of things but of inner light, nor of power but of love, making this truth its own and giving expression to it.

Plato states that, “Education develops in the body and in the soul of the pupil are the perfection he is, capable of”.

4. John Dewey defines education as ‘Education is the process of living through a continuous reconstruction of experiences. It is the development of all those capacities in the individual which will enable him to control his environment and fulfill his possibilities’.

We can conclude from the above definitions that Teaching and training are part and parcel of Education. It is not restricted to the mind and body but includes lightening of soul. Education means to develop an individual for his environment. It is a continuous and life long process involving ample of experiences. Education is a process to facilitate learning, to acquire knowledge, to apply knowledge, to develop understanding and skills. Education may take place formally or informally. Learners may learn with direct or indirect approaches through experiences. Educationists believe that role of educators is to motivate and guide the learner. Education is a process of modification of child’s behavior. And to for the overall development of learner a teacher must understand the general objectives of education such as knowledge, understanding, application of knowledge and developing skills, habits, interest etc. The role of teacher is major and significant to impart knowledge in learners.

Aims of Education

- Development of national values and core elements such as patriotic value, Values of equality, secular values, and values related to dignity of labor and values related to universal brotherhood and understanding.
- To develop skills related to vocations / professions.
- To develop self dependency.
- To create good citizens and ultimately wise human beings.
- Educational philosophy focuses on educational policy, practice and to make required resolution.

Functions of Education

Philosophical Base of Education

Plato defined Philosophy as ‘Knowledge of the nature of different things is philosophy’. Philosophy word has a Greek origin. Lateral meaning of philosophy is ‘love of wisdom’. Education is one of the medium for developing wisdom.

Relationship between philosophy and Education

Philosophy – love of knowledge

Education – acquisition of Knowledge

There are various purpose of educational philosophy such as inspirational purpose, analytical purpose, prescriptive purpose and inquiry purpose that focus on different areas of education.

1. Aims & Objectives

Education is directed for specific goals and objectives in every society. To set the goals of education it is very important to have philosophical view. The aims of education may vary in various country but they all are on the basis of philosophy followed by that particular country such as Hindu philosophy, Islamic philosophy. Generally education is to develop socially and morally sound citizens.

2. Methods & Curriculum

Pedagogy or methodology and curriculum are important aspects of every educational system.

Philosophy provides clarity for following questions regarding education system.

- What teaching methodology should be followed?
- What kind of qualities should a teacher have?
- What subjects and content should be included in curriculum?

Thus, the area of methods and curriculum related to education are focused by educational philosophy.

3. Educational Philosophy

It is a separate branch of philosophy which deals with framing the objectives of education and nature of education. It sets the goals of education according to the specific religion, society, morals and scientific approaches. Further it provides directions to achieve those objectives of the education.

- Philosophy is the science of knowledge. Philosophy is the mother of all sciences.
- Educational philosophy is a branch of applied philosophy.
- All great philosophers have given recommendations for various aspects of education. Being a philosopher they were great educationist.
- Philosophy is a theoretical part while education implements it into practice.
- Philosophy answers thousands of questions pertaining to the various aspects of education.
- Educational philosophy provides directions to frame objectives, core elements, values, curriculum, evaluation pattern and other areas of education context.
- Educational philosophy is a torch light to construct educational principles and policies.

- When educators understand the philosophy behind the education system, curriculum and syllabus, it becomes easy to achieve the objectives of education. Because education is a goal oriented process.

Psychological Base of Education

Educational psychology is the branch of Psychology which deals with various areas of education such as learning, behavioral psychology, theories of learning, motivation, intelligence, adolescent period, objectives of education, need of education, curriculum etc. Following are the main perspectives of education where we find psychological base of education.

➤ Behaviorism

Behavioral psychology states that all behavior can be learned through proper practice and training. Various theories such as operant conditioning explain about how learning takes place. Teacher can use different forms of rewards and reinforcement to develop particular behavior in students. J. B. Watson, an American psychologist who is known as a father of behavioral psychology has developed psychology as an objective study of behavior. He stated that “Give me a dozen healthy infants, well-formed, and my own specified world to bring them up in and I'll guarantee to take any one at random and train him to become any type of specialist I might select – doctor, lawyer, artist, merchant-chief and, yes, even beggar-man and thief, regardless of his talents, penchants, tendencies, abilities, vocations, and race of his ancestors”. According to behaviorism, environment is much more important than heredity in the determination of behavior. Conditioning is the key to understand behavior.

➤ Cognitivism

In recent decades cognitivism became widespread. It deals with the study of several factors such as thinking, memory, emotions, motivation, perception and how do they contribute in the learning process. Cognitive Psychology focuses on understanding how people perceive knowledge, think, learn, remember, and implement information. Educational psychologists are always interested in experiments in order to understand how children get motivated to learn, how do they remember whatever they learn, how do they solve problems and how do they acquire skills. 's Famous psychologist Jean Piaget has stated stages of cognitive development are example of an important developmental theory to study about how children grow intellectually and how do they think at different stages of development. Educational psychologists try to understand what children are capable of at each point of their growth. This may help learners and educators to adopt instructional methods and materials according to age groups.

➤ Constructivism

The theory of constructivist approach is one of the modern learning theories that focus on how children construct their knowledge of various things and concepts. Constructivism studies the influence of social and cultural aspects on the learning process. According to the theoretical framework of Bruner learning is an active process where learners construct own new concepts based upon their knowledge. The learner selects and transforms knowledge, information, constructs hypotheses, and makes conclusions as per cognitive structure which provides meaning and organization to experiences and allows the individual to go beyond the experiences and information. Following are the principles of constructivism.

1. Instruction must be concerned with the experiences and contexts that make the student willing and able to learn.
2. Instruction must be structured so that it can be easily grasped by the student.
3. Instruction should be designed to facilitate extrapolation and or fill in the gaps.

Bruner's theory of constructivism is a general framework for instruction based upon the study of cognition. Jerome Bruner states four major aspects that a theory of instruction should consider. (1) Predisposition towards learning, (2) the ways in which a body of knowledge can be structured so that it can be most readily grasped by the learner, (3) the most effective sequences in which to present material, and (4) the nature and pacing of rewards and punishments. Good methods for structuring knowledge should result in simplifying, generating new propositions, and increasing the manipulation of information.

There is a very complex relation between education and psychology. Psychology is correlated with various aspects of education. And different areas of educational psychology are interrelated with each other. Psychology plays significant role in teaching learning process in education. Teaching methodology, learners' ability, mental status of learner, learning approaches, interaction between teacher and learner, theories of learning, pattern of evaluation are the main areas of educational psychology. Educational psychologists have done many experiments to understand the learning process. And on the basis of these experiments certain theories are proposed in order to understand and improve teaching learning process.

Conclusion

There are ample of factors affecting education and education system. Philosophy and Psychology are always considered as base or pillars of education. Philosophy and Psychology direct education in order to decide- What to teach? How to teach? When to teach? Education is a dynamic and lifelong process takes place from womb to tomb. A person learns from experiences not only in school but also in society or in other life situations. There is an inclusion of Philosophy and Psychology in every type of

direct and indirect learning. Educationist from the field of Philosophy and Psychology do research in various aspects of education in order to understand and improve the education system.

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